

Bend without Fear
Hopes and Possibilities for an Indian Church
Essays in Honour of Professor Kurien Kunnumpuram SJ

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BEND WITHOUT FEAR:

Hopes and Possibilities for an Indian Church; Essays in Honour of Professor Kurien Kunnumpuram SJ

Being true to her Teacher, the Church in India has to be prophetic without fear or favour. In a developing country, the Indian Church has to render her prophetic voice to help guide new and humane structures and institutions. Above all, the Indian Church would have herself to overcome the internal divisions and become a creative, committed and compassionate community. The transformation of the Indian Church as a communion of Local Churches, a light to the nations, may be an inspiration to our nation as well to Bend Without Fear. More than twenty contemporary theologians share their visions and dreams for an Indian Church.

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More than a dozen theologians share their dreams and hopes, visions and aspirations for an Indian Church. The twenty-first century, and may be the third millennium, would be a providential time to let the Church bloom on the Indian soil, rooted and grounded in the culture of this ancient land, the cradle of great religions. The way to become truly Indian is, without a doubt, an art. The articles in this volume are both relevant and committed: relevant both to the modern world and the present India and committed both to the Christian tradition and India heritage. They are also contextual and interdisciplinary.

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Dated: 30.7.2002

sd/- Kurien Kunnumpuram

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